

HISTORICAL SCIENCES

THE MAHALLA SYSTEM IN THE MUSLIM WORLD AS A PLATFORM FOR SOCIAL RELATIONS AND INTERRELIGIOUS DIALOGUE

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Abstract

This article examines the historical formation of the mahalla system in the Muslim world and its role in social and interreligious relations. The mahalla is analyzed as an important social institution that ensures not only territorial organization but also social control, mutual assistance, religious life, and economic cooperation. The study traces the development of the mahalla from early settlements in Mecca and Medina through the Umayyad, Abbasid, and Ottoman periods. Particular attention is given to the coexistence of different religious communities in regions such as the Middle East, Central Asia, and Andalusia. The article concludes that the mahalla system played a significant role in fostering social integration and interreligious interaction while preserving ethnic and religious diversity.

Keywords: Hitat (allocated quarters/plots), mahalla (neighborhood community), Quraysh al-Bitah, Quraysh al-Zawahir, Shi‘b Abu Talib, Umayyads, Abbasids, Mamluks, Ottomans (Ottoman Empire), Central Asian khanates, ra‘is (community leader), sheikh, aksakal (elder), ahdas (urban militia), zu‘ar (urban youth groups), “mixed quarter”.

KIRISH INTRODUCTION

Throughout the history of Muslim societies, the mahalla has been recognized not merely as a territorial unit but also as an important form of social control, mutual assistance, religious and practical life, economic cooperation, and local self-governance. At the same time, the concept of “mahalla” was not uniformly used across all Muslim regions. In Ottoman Turkish cities, it was commonly referred to as *mahalle*; in the Arab world, the term *hitat* was often employed; while in Central Asia, the term *mahalla* remained prevalent.

Modern scholarship demonstrates that it is inaccurate to explain the history of Muslim cities solely through the model of “districts inhabited exclusively by adherents of one religion.” In reality, many cities witnessed both close neighborhood interaction and varying degrees of coexistence among Muslims, Christians, and Jews.

Etymologically, the term *mahalla* derives from the Arabic root *hall* (*halal* and *hulul*), meaning “to settle,” “to reside,” or “to occupy a place.” The word thus refers to “small residential settlements established for permanent or temporary habitation.” With slight linguistic variations, the term has been used in similar meanings throughout the Islamic world.

MAIN PART

Early Formation of Mahallas in Mecca and Medina. Islamic historical sources indicate that the earliest residential settlements in Mecca were established around the Ka‘ba by Qusay ibn Kilab, one of the ancestors of the Prophet Muhammad (peace be upon him). Two major neighborhoods known as *Quraysh al-Bitah* and *Quraysh al-Zawahir* emerged in the city. Historical reports further mention that approximately twelve mahallas existed in Mecca during the early Islamic period. Muslims themselves experienced severe hardship while residing in the quarter of Abu Talib (*Shi‘b Abu Talib*)

during the social and economic boycott imposed upon them.

At the time of the Prophet’s migration (*Hijra*) to Medina, Arab and Jewish tribes lived in relatively distant neighborhoods. Even after the construction of Al-Masjid an-Nabawi, this urban pattern continued, though the city’s spatial organization was rearranged. Peripheral neighborhoods were integrated into the city plan in order to avoid overcrowding, ensure security, and maintain connections between distant settlements and the city center.

During the medieval period, the number of neighborhoods in Medina increased as the city expanded according to circular urban planning models. Some old neighborhoods disappeared while new suburban quarters emerged. Residents of peripheral neighborhoods occasionally enjoyed privileges, particularly regarding taxation [9:70].

Mahalla Organization During the Umayyad and Abbasid Periods. Following the early Islamic conquests, newly established cities developed according to tribal and military principles. The term *hitta* (plural: *hitat*) was used to designate quarters allocated to specific tribes or tribal groups.

Cities such as Basra, Kufa, Fustat, and Kairouan, initially established for military purposes, gradually evolved into religious, political, and cultural centers. Their neighborhoods were organized around central urban institutions such as mosques, administrative headquarters (*dar al-imara*), hospitals, and markets. Each tribe often occupied its own separate quarter.

For instance, every tribe settled in Kufa possessed a distinct neighborhood. Beginning especially in the Umayyad period, mosques and cemeteries also became important structural components of the mahalla system.

The Umayyad governor al-Hajjaj ibn Yusuf (661–714) founded the city of Wasit along both banks of the Tigris River and divided it into four neighborhoods.

Non-Arabs were prohibited from settling on the western bank, while populations brought from Bukhara and Transoxiana were settled on the eastern side. Similar policies were implemented during the Abbasid period in Samarra, where Turks and people from Ferghana were placed in separate and distant quarters.

Over time, streets developed between tribal quarters and functioned both as connecting routes and as boundaries separating neighborhoods. According to Ibn Kathir, during this period the mahalla generated a strong sense of belonging among its inhabitants, to the extent that individuals were sometimes identified by the names of their neighborhoods [7:338].

Urban Diversity and Religious Coexistence. As Muslim cities evolved, ethnic, tribal, professional, and religious forms of organization became increasingly intertwined. In Baghdad, founded according to political and economic priorities, neighborhoods and districts were organized based on ethnic origins and occupations. Such arrangements facilitated the development of urban units with distinct identities.

In Andalusia, Muslims often settled in suburban neighborhoods. During the tenth century, Cordoba contained twenty-one inner-city quarters and twenty-one suburban neighborhoods inhabited primarily by local Muslims (*muwalladun*). Ibn Hawqal recorded that Palermo in Sicily possessed four neighborhoods, one of which, mainly inhabited by Slavic slaves (*saqaliba*), was separated from the sea by a large wall.

In historic Middle Eastern cities incorporated into Muslim rule, urban structures largely preserved their earlier forms while adapting to newly arriving populations. Cities were divided into quarters according to religious and ethnic affiliation, occasionally separated by walls. For example, in Damascus Christians lived in the northeastern section, Jews in the southeastern part, and Muslims in the western districts [1:323–324].

The spread of Islam eastward into Iran and Turkestan also transformed urban organization. By the eleventh century, Central Asian cities had developed a distinctive structure. Walled cities were divided into neighborhoods according to professions, with craftsmen and occupational groups concentrated in separate mahallas. Ibn Battuta observed that people of different ethnic origins, religions, and professions lived in walled neighborhoods, demonstrating the institutionalization of this system [10:394].

The Mahalla in Anatolia and the Ottoman Empire. Beginning in the late eleventh century, Turkic migrations into Anatolia gradually produced new urban settlement patterns. Initially, Byzantine urban structures were largely preserved; however, new cities and neighborhoods emerged over time as Anatolia underwent a process of Turkification.

Religion played a particularly important role in shaping mahallas in Muslim cities. Some scholars defined the mahalla as “the urban quarter inhabited by families belonging to the congregation of the same mosque” [4:69].

Western researchers have frequently considered the division of Muslim cities into ethnic and religious districts as one of their defining characteristics. Yet the existence of non-Muslim neighborhoods in cities such as Kairouan and Wasit indicates that such divisions also

reflected practical considerations of coexistence and communal autonomy rather than rigid segregation.

In Anatolia, individuals belonging to different ethnic and religious groups generally lived within their own neighborhoods. Nevertheless, under Muslim rule this arrangement was not necessarily regarded as discriminatory. During the Ottoman period, members of different religions often found homes as neighbors within predominantly Muslim quarters, particularly in cities such as Istanbul, Bosnia, and Lebanon. Ottoman archival records reveal that Muslims and non-Muslims frequently lived within the same neighborhoods in Anatolian and former Byzantine cities.

Certain occupational groups also resided in quarters named after their professions, such as “Blacksmiths’ Quarter” or “Coal Sellers’ Quarter.”

Social Functions and Governance of the Mahalla. In classical Islamic cities, commercial and residential zones were generally separated. This separation reflected not only distinctions between private and public space but also the relative autonomy of neighborhoods from direct state interference.

Mahallas managed many local affairs independently, strengthening solidarity among residents. Archival documents indicate that residents of different professions often lived side by side within the same neighborhood.

During the Umayyad and Abbasid periods, neighborhoods were administered by figures known as *ra'is* and *sheikh*. The *ra'is* was appointed by government authorities, whereas the *sheikh* gained legitimacy through social recognition. These leaders maintained order, coordinated aid during crises, and mediated local disputes.

In medieval Baghdad, neighborhood residents organized collectively to combat rising theft and insecurity. Urban militia organizations such as the *ahdas* in Syria and Iraq later evolved into youth organizations known as *zu'ar* during the decline of the Mamluk state.

In Ottoman cities, the mahalla became the fundamental administrative unit. Tax records listed residents according to neighborhoods, and collective responsibility was imposed upon mahalla inhabitants. A commonly repeated principle stated that “the residents of the mahalla are collectively responsible for one another.”

Neighborhood imams played a central administrative role, especially until the nineteenth century. They recorded births, deaths, and marriages, supervised local affairs, collected taxes, and acted as intermediaries between residents and judicial authorities. Non-Muslim neighborhoods were similarly administered by rabbis or priests representing their respective religious communities.

Mixed Neighborhoods and Interreligious Relations. For a long time, historiography promoted a simplified model of the “Islamic city” in which Muslims occupied central districts while non-Muslims lived in strictly separate quarters. Scholars such as Janet Abu-Lughod and André Raymond criticized this schematic interpretation, arguing that urban reality was far more complex [5:155–176].

Heather J. Sharkey notes that until the early twentieth century Muslims, Christians, and Jews in the Middle East frequently inhabited “shared worlds,” using the same markets, streets, and urban spaces while speaking common languages [12:1–26].

Court records, property transactions, and wills demonstrate that non-Muslims often purchased or rented houses within Muslim neighborhoods and vice versa. Such coexistence was especially common in markets, ports, and artisan districts. Shared institutions such as streets, water sources, bathhouses, bakeries, workshops, and systems of neighborhood solidarity reinforced daily interaction despite religious differences [6:831–863].

Studies of Ottoman Istanbul by Cem Behar and Fariba Zarinebaf reveal that many neighborhoods were socially and religiously mixed rather than homogeneous. In districts such as Galata, Balat, and Hasköy, Muslims, Jews, and Christians often lived side by side [14:79–85].

Similarly, Micah Campos’ research on Ottoman Jerusalem demonstrates that even neighborhoods appearing integrated on a broad scale contained localized clusters of specific religious communities [2:133–169].

In Central Asia, especially in Bukhara, the mahalla functioned as both a territorial and spiritual institution. Although a distinct Jewish quarter existed in Bukhara, Jewish residents actively participated in the city’s commercial life and maintained close relations with Muslim communities.

CONCLUSION

The coexistence of different religious communities within the framework of the mahalla system represents a historical reality in the Muslim world. The mahalla often enabled diverse groups to live together while preserving their religious and ethnic distinctions. This coexistence was particularly visible in the practical dimensions of urban life, including trade, social interaction, and neighborhood cooperation.

Experiences from Ottoman Istanbul, Jerusalem, Damascus, and Central Asia demonstrate that the mahalla simultaneously preserved religious identities and fostered everyday neighborly and economic relations. Consequently, the mahalla system should be understood not only as an internal communal structure of Muslim societies but also as one of the foundational institutions of multi-confessional urban civilization.

Thus, the historical experience of the mahalla provides important insights for contemporary discussions concerning social integration, intercultural dialogue, and peaceful coexistence in pluralistic societies.

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